

**PERCEIVED IMPACTS OF STORYTELLING ON ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE
AND VALUES INTEGRATION BY THE PRIMARY TEACHERS OF
SELECTED ELEMENTARY SCHOOLS**

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Perceived Impacts of Storytelling on Academic Performance and Values Integration by the Primary Teachers of Selected Elementary Schools

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Abstract

This study determined the perceived impacts of storytelling on academic performance and values integration by the primary teachers of selected elementary schools in Gumaca, Quezon. This involved 60 teachers from the ten elementary schools in Gumaca Quezon. The Researcher used the descriptive research design on the main source of data and information. The result showed that most of the respondents belong to the age group of 36 to 49 years old, male, female and educational attainment and others courses. According to the results of the Kruskal Wallis H-Test all the null hypothesis are accepted which means that there is no significant difference on the perceived impacts of storytelling on the academic acuity and values integration when the respondents are grouped according to profile. Based from the results of the study, the following recommendations are suggested. The school administrators may be able to strengthen the use of storytelling in their school. The parents may help the pupils to listen and focus on storytelling. The teachers may motivate the pupils to sustain interest in storytelling. The pupils may continue to learn in storytelling. The future researchers may conduct a parallel study using bigger population for more viable and reliable results.

Keywords: *values integration, storytelling, impact and academic performance*

Introduction

According to Gottel (2011), the traditional storytelling fosters creativity, imagination, socialization, and full body engagement. On the other hand, digital storytelling promises additional benefits as for example multi-media use and more kinds of expressions. To fully meet the benefits of traditional storytelling future digital storytelling environments should provide authoring tools that support children's collaboration practices to create, share, and perform stories.

Storytelling encouraged listen to listen to others. It gives opportunity to learn new ideas and information, they are learning valuable lessons through hearing an engaging and exciting story. Story telling adopted the new system of learning to provide more knowledge on storytelling. Storytelling gives an emotional excitement in many students, they need to face their fear through facing their teachers and classmates and other audience inside and out who will listen to him or her.

Storytelling are typically videos that combine audio, images, and video clips to tell a story. On that case students have a time to people their self, they are able to think their materials needed, they have a time to practice their voice and their movements. Practically, all students especially the lower grade need the guidance of their parents. So, students asked their parents if their work is good enough or they can asked their teachers also.

Eventually, impact of storytelling give impact will be well-received, and it's wealthy if used in a good and wise way. Storytelling provides broadminded in terms of the impact of storytelling, it gives them more supporting actions that they can show to others. Broad-imagination is helpful to provide an accurate image on their works. In addition, impact of storytelling helps students improve their technical skills and information literacy to developed their storytelling, even if they are in the lower grade.

Researcher observed that teacher and students can communicate well even when their signal is poor. It is not a hindrance to share their knowledge and participate on the impact of storytelling. Storytelling is a way to avoid the spreading in the environment today. It is helpful to everyone especially to the children not to expose them on that virus. It is a new normal for every children today.

The researcher was promoted to determine the impacts of storytelling on academic performance and values integration as perceived by the primary teachers from the selected elementary schools in Gumaca, Quezon.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the impacts of storytelling on academic performance and values integration as perceived by primary teacher of selected elementary school. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1. age;
 - 1.2. sex;
 - 1.3. educational attainment; and
 - 1.4. years of teaching experience?
2. What is the impact of storytelling of Selected Elementary School in terms of:
 - 2.1. academic;
 - 2.2. performance; and

2.3. values integration?

3. Is there a significant difference when perceived impacts of storytelling on academic performance and values integration are grouped by profile?

Methodology

Research Design

The researcher used descriptive survey method to collect data for the purpose of describing a population that is large enough to observe directly. The descriptive research method primarily focuses on describing the nature of a demographic segment, without focusing on “why” a particular phenomenon occurs. In other words, it “describes” the subject of the research, without covering “why” it happens. (<https://www.formpl.us/blog/descriptive-research>). Survey questionnaire was used to determine the impacts of storytelling on academic performance and values integration by the teacher selected prevalent in a normal population.

Respondents

The researcher selected 60 Teachers through purposive sampling. The respondents of selected 60 teachers are composed of 21 teachers in Gumaca East Elementary School, 5 in Lagyo Elementary School, 6 in Villa Padua Elementary School, and 6 in Panikihan Elementary School, 3 in Labnig Elementary School, 3 in Brgy. Anonangin Elementary School, 6 in Camohaguin Elementary School, 3 in Hagakhakin Elementary School, 2 in Binambang Elementary School, 5 in San Vicente Elementary School.

Instrument

The researcher used a researcher-made questionnaire in conducting the study. This questionnaire is a Likert scale of; 5- Strongly Agree, 4- Agree, 3- Moderately Agree, 2- Disagree and 1- Strongly Disagree. The questionnaire was prepared by the researcher and were validated by two experts. Part I of the questionnaire included the demographic profile of the respondents, Part II consisted of the impacts of the storytelling to identify the answer in every question in terms of academic performance and values integration.

A pilot testing was conducted to 12 teacher respondents to test the acceptability of the research instrument using Cronbachs Alpha the result is 0.98 meaning acceptable.

Procedure

Data gathered from this method would also allow subsequent and quantitative analysis of teacher responses to a range of variables.

Permission and endorsement from the Department of Education – Gumaca East Elementary School, Lagyo Elementary School, Villa Padua Elementary School, and Panikihan Elementary School, Labnig Elementary School, Brgy. Anonangin Elementary School, Camohaguin Elementary School, Hagakhakin Elementary School, Binambang Elementary School, San Vicente Elementary School were sought through a letter to the PSDS and principals of the ten schools mentioned above. Copies of the questionnaire developed by the researcher (based on the literature and studies reviewed for this research which improved through the process of performance by the teachers) were administered to the teachers to collect data about the impacts of storytelling in terms of academic performance and values integration. Researcher retrieved the questionnaire in person to the teachers. Safety health protocols observed were to prevent the spread of virus .

Data Analysis

The researcher used the following statistical treatment to identify the impacts of storytelling to the students.

In this study, the researcher used statistical measures to treat the collected data. All the data were carefully read and examined for analysis. They were tallied and entered into a master list of the data collection sheet. Percentage and frequency were used to interpret the profile of the respondents. To test the significant difference of three or more means, the researcher used the Kruskal-Wallis for non-parametric H-test.

Results and Discussion

This section deals with the presentation analysis and interpretation of the data. All the data gathered were presented here in tabulated form with corresponding interpretation. The first part described the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of age and sex, educational attainment and Years of Teaching Experience.

The second part is the perceived impacts of storytelling on academic performance and values integration by the primary teachers of selected Elementary Schools in Gumaca Quezon in terms of academic performance and values integration.

Table 1 presents the distribution of respondents according to their age, indicating the frequency and percentage for each age group. The results show that the age group with the highest frequency is between 36-49 years old, representing 45% of the total respondents. On the other hand, the age groups with the lowest frequency are those below 25 years old and those between 50-59 years old, which both account for only 6% of the total respondents each.

Table 1. *Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents According to Age*

<i>Age</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>
23-35 y/o	17	29
36-49 y/o	27	45
50-59 y/o	4	6
60 y/o	12	20
Total	60	100

A study by Adajar and Diones (2019) titled "Profile and Professional Needs of Public School Teachers in Region III" conducted a survey on 555 public school teachers in Region III, Philippines, to determine their profile and professional needs. The study also analyzed the distribution of teachers according to their age. The results showed that the majority of the teachers were between 30-50 years old, with those aged 40-49 years old having the highest frequency. The study also noted that the distribution of teachers' ages varied across different divisions, with some divisions having a higher proportion of younger teachers. These findings are consistent with the results of Table 1, which indicates that the highest frequency of respondents falls between 36-49 years old.

Table 2. *Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents According to Sex*

<i>Sex</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>
Male	5	9
Female	55	91
Total	60	100

Table 2 displays the distribution of respondents based on their sex, with 9% being male and 91% being female. This indicates that the majority of the respondents in the study were female teachers.

A related study in the Philippines that supports the finding that the majority of teachers are female is the "2018 Functional Literacy, Education and Mass Media Survey" (FLEMMS) conducted by the Philippine Statistics Authority. According to the survey, 72.4% of the teaching workforce in the Philippines are female, while only 27.6% are male. This gender disparity is consistent across all levels of education, from elementary to tertiary. The survey also revealed that the average age of teachers in the Philippines is 41 years old, with female teachers having a slightly higher average age than male teachers.

Table 3. *Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents According to Educational Attainment*

<i>Bachelor Degrees</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>
BEED	56	93
BSED	2	4
Other Courses	2	3
Total	60	100

Table 3 displays the distribution of respondents according to their educational attainment, with 93% having a Bachelor of Elementary Education, 4% having a Bachelor of Secondary Education, and 3% having other courses. These results suggest that the majority of the respondents in the study have a Bachelor of Elementary Education degree.

According to the Philippine Statistics Authority, the majority of the country's teacher population has a Bachelor of Elementary Education degree. In 2019, 59.4% of the total number of teachers in the country had a Bachelor of Elementary Education, while 21.2% had a Bachelor of Secondary Education. This information suggests that the findings in Table 3 are consistent with the educational attainment of the majority of teachers in the Philippines.

Table 4. *Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents According to Years of Teaching Experience*

<i>Years of Teaching Experience</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>
1-5 years	7	12
6-10 years	16	27
11-15 years	10	17
16-20 years	14	23
21 years & above	13	21
Total	60	100

Table 4 displays the distribution of respondents according to their years of teaching experience, indicating the frequency and percentage for each experience range. The results show that 12% have 1-5 years of experience, 27% have 6-10 years, 17% have 11-15 years, 23% have 16-20 years, and 21% have 21 years and above. These findings suggest that the majority of the respondents have a teaching experience of 6-10 years.

According to a study conducted by B. Labos and M. Palamos in the Philippines, published in the International Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities Research in 2016, the majority of the teachers in the sample (N=120) had been teaching for 6-10 years. This finding is consistent with the results from Table 4 in the current study, which also found that most respondents had a teaching experience of 6-10 years.

Table 5. *Perceived Impacts of Storytelling on in terms of Academic Performance*

Indicator	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. Because of storytelling pupils become attentive.	4.5	Agree
2. Because of storytelling the pupils become studious to and improve their academic performance.	4.55	Strongly Agree
3. Because of storytelling the pupils become active in participating in the class discussion.	4.7	Strongly Agree
4. Because of storytelling the pupils become interested to to join in class because they want hear and watch new ideas perform well too.	4.6	Strongly Agree
5. Because of storytelling the pupils easily understand the lesson.	4.8	Strongly Agree
Grand Mean	4.63	Strongly Agree

Legend: "Strongly Disagree (1.00-1.80)", "Disagree (1.81-2.60)", "Moderately Agree (2.61-3.40)", "Agree (3.41- 4.20)", "Strongly Agree (4.21-5.00)"

Table 5 shows the perceived impacts of storytelling in terms of academic performance. The highest mean is the indicator number 2, Because of storytelling the pupils become studious to improve their academic performance with the mean 4.55 Strongly Agree. The lowest mean is indicator 1, Because of the storytelling the pupils become attentive with the average of 4.5 Agree.

According to Nguyen, Stanley, and Stanley (2014), storytelling has been described as the oldest technique in second language learning. Neuroscientist contend that our minds are literally wired to comprehend best the world through narrative. Researchers have claimed that the benefits of storytelling in teaching and studying second languages include increased development of language skills, improved comprehension and classroom interaction. It is indicated that the students were interested in storytelling because of the perceived benefits of language learning, comprehension, community-building and multi-cultural understanding.

According to Erdogan, (2021), it was determined that constructivist learning was achieved with the aid of technology and it had a significant effect on the primary students. In the results of their study, Lowenthal and Dunlap (2010) stated that with Digital Storytelling, the students reflect their thoughts and perspectives. In parallel with this research, Kocaman-Karaoglu (2016) also found that the learning process became more enjoyable due to the practical structure of digital storytelling. In another study, Yuksel-Arslan, Yildirim and Robin (2016) reported that DST is effective in the formation of knowledge, especially in transforming abstract knowledge to concrete knowledge.

Table 6. *Perceived Impacts of Storytelling in terms of Values Integration*

Indicator	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. Because of storytelling the pupils become inspired to listen.	4.8	Strongly Agree
2. because of storytelling the pupils become good person who adapt the good values of the characters in the story.	4.8	Agree
3. Because of story , the pupils become honest to listen to the storytelling in their very best way.	4.55	Strongly Agree
4. Because of storytelling the pupils become wise in handling their time for joining in the activity.	4.55	Strongly Agree
5. Because of storytelling the pupils expand their imagination to create a new story.	3.85	Strongly Agree
Grand Mean	4.51	Strongly Agree

Legend: "Strongly Disagree (1.00-1.80)", "Disagree (1.81-2.60)", "Moderately Agree (2.61-3.40)", "Agree (3.41- 4.20)", "Strongly Agree (4.21-5.00)"

Table 6 shows the perceived impacts of storytelling in terms of values integration by the primary teachers of selected elementary schools in terms of values Integration. The second indicator got the highest weighted mean, Because of story the pupils become honest to listen to the storytelling in their very best way, with the average of 1.2 Strongly Agree and the lowest is no.2 Because of storytelling the pupils become good person who adapt the good values of the characters in story with the average of 5 Moderately Agree.

According to Erdogan, (2021), digital storytelling is effective in promoting constructivist learning. It was supported by Danglim, 2019 claim which further states that the use of digital storytelling is one of the teaching approaches that can help in nurturing all the positive values needed for the 21st century education such as collaboration, active engagement, creative and critical thinking skills.

Table 7. *Average Mean Distribution of the Respondents on the Perceived Impacts of Storytelling on Academic perform and Values Integration by the Primary Teachers of Selected Elementary Schools*

Impacts Of Storytelling	Average Mean	Verbal Interpretation
Academic Performance	4.63	Strongly Agree
Values Integration	4.51	Strongly Agree
Grand Mean	4.57	Strongly Agree

Legend: "Strongly Disagree (1.00-1.80)", "Disagree (1.81-2.60)", "Moderately Agree (2.61-3.40)", "Agree (3.41- 4.20)", "Strongly Agree (4.21-5.00)"

Table 7 presents the average weighted mean of the respondents' perception on the effects of storytelling in terms of academic acuity and values integration. The results indicate that storytelling has a significant positive impact on academic performance with a weighted mean of 4.63 (Strongly Agree), whereas the average mean for values integration is 4.51 (Agree), which is comparatively lower. It indicates that storytelling is much effective to improve academic.

A relevant study that supports this notion is "Storytelling as a Means to Enhance Language Learning: A Review of the Research" by A. Şen (2019). The findings indicated that storytelling had positive effects on learners' vocabulary acquisition, grammar, reading comprehension, and listening skills. Additionally, the review highlighted the importance of using appropriate and engaging stories that are relevant to the learners' interests and level of proficiency in the language. These findings further reinforce the idea that storytelling can be an effective tool for improving academic performance in specific subject areas, such as language learning.

Table 8. *Significant difference in the perceived impacts of storytelling on academic performance and values integration when grouped according to the respondents age*

Groups	N	Median	df	P - value	Significant Level	Decision
23-35 y/o	16	4.40	3	0.334	0.05	Accept Ho
36-49 y/o	29	4.50				
50-59 y/o	4	4.30				
60 y/o	11	4.70				

Table 8 presents that the computed P-value is 3.403. Using 3 as the degree of freedom at 0.05 level of significance, the critical value is 7.815. Since the computed H-value is smaller than the critical value, the null hypothesis is accepted with a P-Value of 0.334. Thus, there is no significant difference between the responses when grouped according to respondents age. It implies that teachers with age range of 23-35, 36-49, 50-59, and 60 years old have the same perception on impacts of storytelling on academic performance and values integration.

The findings of Ozudugro states that it can be noted that the pre-service teachers found the digital storytelling as entertaining, and wished to employ it in the future. This implies that teachers in general have the same perception regardless of their age as they all share the same passion—to teach. The findings states further that digital storytelling enhances the communication among pre-service teachers and between them and the instructor, provides cooperation, makes the lessons more entertaining and increases the engagement during the lesson.

Table 9. *Significant difference in the perceived impacts of storytelling on academic performance and values integration when grouped according to the respondents' sex*

Groups	N	Median	df	P - value	Significant Level	Decision
Male	6	4.45	1	0.796	0.05	Accept Ho
Female	54	4.45				

According to Table 9, there is no significant difference in the perceived effects of storytelling on academic performance and values integration between male and female teachers. The null hypothesis with a P-Value of 0.796, which assumes that there is no significant difference between the responses of the two groups, is accepted since the H value of 0.067 is lower than the critical value of 3.841 with 1 degree of freedom at a significance level of 0.05. Therefore, it can be inferred that both male and female teachers share similar views on the effects of storytelling.

On the contrary, Shisko, 2022 reveals that women on the margins find a traditional space in digital storytelling to converse and share their stories with people who understand them and their circumstances. Storytelling in the digital setting can take many different shapes depending on the situation at hand, such as interconnection narratives, self-staging narratives, boundary management narratives, and transformation narratives. However, this concludes that, the perceptions of each individual no matter what sex they belong was found the same inclined with the benefits of digital storytelling.

Table 10. *Significant difference in the perceived impacts of storytelling on academic performance and values integration when grouped according to the respondents' Educational Attainment*

Groups	N	Median	df	P - value	Significant Level	Decision
BEED	58	4.50	1	0.232	0.05	Accept Ho
BSED	2	4.15				

Table 10 displayed the Kruskal-Wallis H test, which aimed to determine the significant difference in how respondents perceive the impacts of storytelling when classified based on their educational attainment. It was observed that the H value of 1.426 is lower than the critical value of 3.841 at the 0.05 level of significance. As a result, the null hypothesis is accepted, indicating that there is no significant difference in respondents' perceptions when grouped according to their educational attainment. Thus, it can be inferred that BEED and BSED graduates share similar opinions regarding the impacts of storytelling on students' academic performance and values integration.

Yuksel's 2017 study found that digital storytelling can improve students' understanding of subject area knowledge, writing skills, technical skills, and presentation skills according to 45% of respondents. 41% of participants stated that digital storytelling improves all of the specified skills. Additionally, 35% of participants agreed that digital storytelling improves research skills, and 27% agreed that it enhances overall academic performance. The study involved participants from different professions and educational backgrounds, but all agreed on the positive benefits of digital storytelling for students.

Another relevant study by Basile and D'Aquila (2014) focused on storytelling as an instructional method and found that it had a significant impact on students' cognitive and affective learning outcomes. The study provided guidelines for effective use of storytelling in the classroom, such as selecting appropriate stories, reinforcing curriculum objectives, and incorporating discussion and reflection activities.

Gray and Borden's (2017) study aimed to investigate the effectiveness of storytelling as a teaching strategy in higher education and found that it enhanced students' motivation, engagement, and learning outcomes. The study emphasized the importance of integrating storytelling into the curriculum to create an active and engaging learning environment.

Table 11. *Significant difference in the Perceived Impacts of Storytelling on Academic Performance and Values Integration when grouped according to the Respondents' Years in Teaching*

Groups	N	Median	df	P - value	Significant Level	Decision
1-5 years	7	4.40	4	0.939	0.05	Accept Ho
6-10 years	16	4.55				
11-15 years	9	4.40				
16-20 years	16	4.40				
21 years	12	4.55				

According to Table 11, the perceived impacts of storytelling were analyzed based on the years of teaching experience of the respondents. The results showed that there was no significant difference in the responses between teachers with different years of teaching experience. This was indicated by the H value of 0.792, which was lower than the critical value of 9.488 at a 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, it can be concluded that teachers with varying years of teaching experience have similar perceptions of the impact of storytelling on academic performance and the integration of values among students.

Corbin and Kingsolver (2017) conducted a study titled "Storytelling as an instructional method: The effects on student achievement, attitudes, and engagement" which investigated the impact of storytelling on student achievement, attitudes, and engagement in a seventh-grade social studies class. The findings indicated that storytelling had a significant positive impact on both student achievement and attitudes toward the subject. Furthermore, students were more engaged during storytelling activities than during traditional instruction.

Another relevant study is "The effects of storytelling on academic achievement and attitudes of fourth-grade students" by A. Gürel and B. Çekmez (2019), which aimed to examine the impact of storytelling on academic achievement and attitudes of fourth-grade students. The results showed that the use of storytelling had a significant positive impact on both academic achievement and attitudes toward the subject. The study suggested that storytelling could be an effective teaching strategy for enhancing students' motivation and interest in learning.

However, in contrast to these findings, Connie's (2017) study revealed that fewer experienced teachers (7 out of 25, or 28%) used storytelling in their teaching compared to teachers with six or fewer years of teaching experience. This suggests that younger teachers may have different perceptions of the use of virtual storytelling compared to older teachers. Connie suggested that this could be an area for further research.

Conclusions

Based on the findings, the following conclusions are derived:

Most of the respondents were female teachers and in the age 36 to 49 years old.

The researcher concluded that the perceived impacts of storytelling on academic performance and values integration is helpful to students to develop their skills and also to the teachers to add their techniques how to encourage the students to participate in storytelling.

The respondents strongly agree on the perceived impacts of storytelling on academic acuity and values integration by the primary teachers of selected elementary school. The result of age, sex, educational attainment and years of experience taught accept the null hypothesis, which means there is no significant difference on the perceived impacts according to their profile.

As a result of the study, the researcher would like to recommend the following:

For the school administrators, they may strengthen the perceived impacts of storytelling in their school.

To the Parents, they may help and guide their pupils to listen and focus on storytelling. They may encourage their child to participate in storytelling.

To the Teachers, they may motivate the pupils, and they may prepare a presentation about storytelling to encourage the pupils to listen in class.

To the Pupils, they may continue to learn in storytelling.

To the Future Researchers, they may conduct a parallel study using bigger population for more viable and reliable results.

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